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A Consequence of AI on Engineering Education: Growing Demand for Deeper Understanding

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INTRODUCTION

The revolution of information technology goes on, and one of the biggest ongoing changes in engineering is the development of artificial intelligence (AI). According to many views, during the following decades AI will replace a share of even such duties that are still today considered as expert jobs. According to Russell and Norvig, AI attempts to build intelligent entities. From the recent point of view, the emphasis of development has changed from the traditional approach of AI to machine learning. In the traditional approach, machine was given data and the rules, and the results were gained as an output. The essential difference in machine learning is that a machine is able to deduce rules. Thus, if machine is given the data and the answers, the rules will be the output. Consequently, machines are already able to prove mathematical theorems and to diagnose diseases. [1]

From engineering education point of view, it is of course important to stay on the crest of the wave and to include topical immediate engineering skills of AI in engineering curricula. However, another highly important goal is to promote such engineering skills that cannot be replaced with AI. As economic pressure and eagerness for increasing efficiency in universities have already decreased the role of thorough learning of fundamentals in engineering studies, recent development of AI may continue the trend, if caution is not taken. In this paper, the main scope is to promote such *long-term engineering skills* that cannot be easily replaced with AI. In engineering, they are closely related to higher learning, since they mainly arise from deeper understanding of scientific fundamentals.

1 ABOUT HIGHER LEARNING IN ENGINEERING EDUCATION

How do we define higher learning in engineering education? According to Keeling and Hersh, higher learning requires meaning making, as opposed to memorisation and just-in-time ingestion of facts. Higher learning prepares students to think creatively and critically, and to communicate effectively and actively. In order to figure out how new knowledge is linked to prior one, a deeper meaning of new knowledge has to be uncovered. Otherwise these links easily remain at least a bit unclear [2]. Consequently, a coherent and interconnected structure starting from the fundamentals of engineering substance is needed to truly gain higher learning [3]. We suggest that this kind of solid structure of substance is a necessary condition for higher learning in engineering education.

But how do we implement such a structure in engineering education? Everything starts from such thorough understanding of fundamentals, which during the history of science has been promoted by for example Albert Einstein and Richard Feynman. Then, we are talking about utilising hierarchical structure of natural sciences in engineering education. With the wise words of Feynman: "The goal is to understand basic phenomena in terms of the smallest set of fundamental laws." [4]

The hierarchical structure of natural sciences is described in *Fig. 1*. Although the all-encompassing theoretical framework of physics, *theory of everything*, still remains incomplete, we are constantly heading towards it [5]. Theory of everything represents the most *general* laws of physics, from where more *concrete* laws of different fields of engineering arise. Thus, the explanation of the structure presented in *Fig. 1* is culminated in the words generality and concretisation. When we recede from the theory of everything, concretisation increases. In practice this means that more and more details get fixed. As concretisation increases, engineering models get less general. And on the contrary, generality increases when we approach the theory of everything. In engineering modelling, we are always located on a certain level of concretisation, which are represented by dotted circles in *Fig. 1*. Consequently, we always have a certain set of necessary rules, which lay the foundation for modelling there. The dots in *Fig. 1* represent these necessary rules, which we call cornerstones. Thus, according to Feynman's principles, on each level of concretisation we utilise the smallest set of fundamental laws to carry out modelling.

Fig. 1. Hierarchical structure of natural sciences [6].

In order to demonstrate the structure presented in *Fig. 1*, let's take an example. In electrical engineering, electromagnetic fields and waves represent more general level of modelling than circuit analysis. Thus, circuit analysis is more concrete. This simply comes from the fact that all the rules used in circuit analysis arise from more general laws of electromagnetic fields and waves by fixing some details. Thus, by fixing certain details, Kirchhoff's laws arise from Maxwell's equations. Because Maxwell's equations are more general than Kirchhoff's laws, the former can be used to model circuits, but the latter cannot be used to model fields and waves. This is the basic idea behind the terms general and concrete.

One essential detail in *Fig. 1* is to understand that the restrictions and assumptions validating the cornerstones on a certain level of concretisation always come from more general level of modelling. This is closely related to long-term engineering skills, which are not easily replaced with AI. For example, we can carry out the tasks of circuit analysis by Kirchhoff's laws only, but if we don't have understanding about more general Maxwell's equations, we lack self-criticism towards the results of modelling. This is important detail when considering the role of AI in engineering modelling. There will probably be no problems to solve unambiguous tasks of circuit analysis with AI, but we can easily generate situations, where the models of circuit analysis are not valid. Then, we are dealing with such deeper understanding that is much more difficult to replace with AI.

1.1 Problem of excessive efficiency in engineering education

During the current millennium, a global worry about the state of higher learning in higher education has arisen [2], [7]. One powerful statement was given at World Education Day 2017 conference, where the Nobel Prize winner Shuji Nakamura called for profundity and deeper understanding of scientific fundamentals in university education. He was worried and even angry about the recent efficiency-driven development [8].

The problem of excessive efficiency in engineering education refers to a general economy-driven development of current millennium. Mainly due to economical reasons, many universities have practically been forced to increase the number of accessed and graduated students, and at the same time, another goal has been to decrease the duration of graduation. In order to fulfil these quantitative goals, a common action in engineering education has been to invest in more concrete specialised studies and consequently, to decrease to role of scientific fundamentals. For example in Finland, worry about the reduced role of fundamentals in engineering education has already been a newsworthy event in the national news [9], [10].

The problem can be illustrated with the aid of *immediate* and *long-term engineering skills*. Immediate engineering skills mainly arise from the ability to utilise different engineering tools, which are used to solve versatile engineering problems. On the other hand, long-term engineering skills are closely related to understanding the assumptions and restrictions behind engineering tools [11]. In engineering education, the appropriate balance between immediate and long-term engineering skills is more or less an endless dilemma. However, due to excessive efficiency, recent development of engineering education has clearly overemphasised immediate engineering skills at the expense of thorough learning of fundamentals. And when the growing role of AI in engineering tasks is taken into account, we are honestly worried about this recent development of engineering education.

2 METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH: METHOD OF CORNERSTONES

In order to clarify the roles of immediate and long-term engineering skills, method of cornerstones was created. The big goal was to ensure and strengthen the role of scientific fundamentals in engineering education regardless of decreasing financial resources. In this chapter we present the basic principles of the method and its application to electrical engineering education in undergraduate level.

Implementation of the method of cornerstones to engineering education can be divided into two phases. In the phase 1, immediate engineering skills are emphasised by building modelling methods from the smallest set of fundamental rules, which we call cornerstones. In the phase 2, long-term engineering skills are promoted by questioning the validity of cornerstones. As already mentioned, this requires more general understanding about the assumptions validating the cornerstones.

2.1 Phase 1: building the modelling methods from cornerstones

As an example, we have implemented the method of cornerstones to education of electrical engineering at Tampere University of Applied Sciences. The work continues and evolves year after year, but we already have some concrete results of the experiment.

The implementation of the method of cornerstones was started four years ago from the first course of electrical engineering curriculum: direct current (DC) circuit analysis. This course has a crystal clear learning goal: how to systematically analyse electric circuits in such a way that, in the end, complicated circuits are not more difficult to solve than simple ones; they are just more laborious. And particularly DC circuits were chosen, since we wanted to emphasise the principles of solving the circuits and, at the same time, keep the electrical variables as simple as possible.

The substance of DC circuit analysis is pretty much summarised in *Fig. 2*. The house of DC circuits stands on three cornerstones, which represent the fundamental rules to solve any circuit. Thus, according to Feynman's principles, these three cornerstones represent the smallest set of fundamental laws to carry out modelling on this level of concretisation. The methods written inside the house are not fundamental rules. Instead, they are the modelling methods deduced from the cornerstones. Thus, they are not necessarily required to solve any DC circuits, but their existence is justified from decreasing the required work to solve problems. However, essential observation is that the methods written inside the house are not independent rules in any way, they just represent different options to apply the cornerstones. Consequently, immediate engineering skills mainly arise from the ability to apply different methods to solve DC circuits. On the other hand, long-term engineering skills are mainly related to deeper understanding behind the modelling methods; how do they arise from the cornerstones, and what are the assumptions validating the cornerstones.

Fig. 2. Cornerstones and methods of DC electric circuits [6].

In practice, these principles were implemented to teaching in the following way. In the very first lessons of the course, the frame of reference is presented. Thus, the house of DC circuit analysis presented in *Fig. 2* is first positioned in the bigger modelling picture of electrical engineering. The idea of this is to show students that modelling of electromagnetic fields and waves and various applications of circuit analysis represent only different aspects of the same scientific phenomena. Then, it is briefly presented how the cornerstones of DC circuit analysis are related to more general laws of electromagnetic fields and waves. With this we want to emphasise that the cornerstones of circuit analysis are not unquestioned rules, but instead, they arise from more general Maxwell's equations with certain assumptions. Then, it is underlined that in DC circuit analysis we will not question the validity of cornerstones. They are assumed to be valid in any situation confronted in the course.

Then, after this introductory section, the essential substance of the course is presented to students. The building of systematic competence to analyse electric circuits is started from directly applying the cornerstones to solve the circuits. Thus, students will first learn how to analyse DC circuits by using the cornerstones only. A significant amount of contact lessons is invested in this learning goal. Only after mastering the utilisation of cornerstones, different methods of DC circuit analysis are deduced from the cornerstones. This comprises derivation of all the methods included in the house of *Fig. 2*. All the time it is emphasised to students that all the methods, starting from the rule of series-connected resistors and ending

to Thevenin equivalent, only arise from different options to apply the cornerstones. No specific method is necessarily required to analyse a circuit, since they all arise from the same foundation. The benefit of the methods compared to direct utilisation of cornerstones mainly comes from reduced workload and maybe more fluent solution of the problem.

The latter half of the course is more traditional one, since it is spent among learning the different methods to solve DC circuits. However, the primary learning goal of the course is to gain systematic ability to solve electric circuits. Thus, primary goal is not in learning different methods. This is where we give students the total freedom. All the different ways to solve DC circuit are carefully presented to students, and all the different ways are also practised in order to gain necessary routine. However, we don't want to force students to use a certain method, since they all arise from the same foundation. Thus, students have the freedom to solve electric circuits in such a way that they personally experience worthwhile and convenient. According to our experience, students' variety of personal preference to solve electric circuits in different ways is surprisingly rich.

2.2 Phase 2: questioning the validity of cornerstones

The key feature in the method of cornerstones is to present the substance in a systematic and coherent way by using the smallest set of fundamental rules on a certain level of concretisation. Due to its strong fundamental theory, electrical engineering offers a great example here, but the similar structure can also be found from other fields of engineering. In the phase 1, the level of concretisation and the corresponding cornerstones are fixed, and methods of modelling are deduced from the cornerstones. Then, in the phase 2, the validity of cornerstones is questioned by finding out their premises.

It has to be emphasized that we are dealing with undergraduate level here. Consequently, our main goal in promoting long-term engineering skills is a little bit different than in graduate level. In order to understand the assumptions behind the cornerstones of DC circuit analysis, the knowledge of electromagnetic fields and waves is required. However, they are not studied in a traditional way. Instead, our goal is to increase the responsibility of an engineer carrying out modelling tasks. In practice this means that we question the validity of cornerstones by arranging such learning situations, where cornerstones are invalid. As an example related to *Fig. 2*, we can arrange such situation in a laboratory, where for example Kirchhoff's voltage law is invalid. The main assumption behind this cornerstone is that the magnetic flux through a mesh doesn't vary with time. Magnetic flux is a quantity of electromagnetic fields, so more general knowledge is required here. By positioning a DC circuit in the vicinity of a transformer we can easily arrange a situation, where Kirchhoff's voltage law is invalid. Then we ask students to model the situation as a DC circuit, and also make measurements in a laboratory. Consequently, measured and modelled results do not match, and then students need to figure out, where does the difference come from. With such situations violating the validity of cornerstones we want to increase the self-criticism and responsibility of students in modelling. Another goal is to motivate students towards more general models of electrical engineering in order to gain deeper understanding of their modelling tools.

3 LEARNING RESULTS

In undergraduate level at Tampere University of Applied Sciences the method of cornerstones has been used for four years now to teach the courses of circuit analysis of

electrical engineering. This chapter presents some learning results of the experiment carried out in the substance of DC circuit analysis.

Altogether about 35 hours of contact lessons were organised with the principles presented in chapter 2. In addition, all the materials were available in the forms of short videos and pdf documents in the website of the course. Traditional exam is used as the assessment, since, in the end, it tests very well the learning goals of the course. On the other hand, the exam can also be considered untraditional, since its essential feature is the freedom of method. Thus, students are not forced to use any certain method in any problem of the exam. There are altogether four problems, and six points is the maximum of each problem. Thus, the total maximum is 24 points. Problems 1-3 are typical DC circuit analysis problems with increasing complexity, and in problem 4 students are asked to find Thevenin's equivalent for a certain circuit.

Results of the exam during the experiment of four academic years can be seen in *Fig. 3*. During one academic year the number of attending students has been between 40 and 50, and accordingly the total number of students during four academic years is 191. As the maximum number of points in the exam is 24, it can be seen from *Fig. 3* that the average is about 20 points. Naturally, there are many details that cannot be deduced from these results, but the big picture is still quite clear. Students really learn the fundamental principles of DC circuit analysis very well. And maybe surprisingly, the variety of different ways that students use to solve the problems is really a rich one. More precisely, in addition to the solutions based on plain cornerstones, also all the methods presented in *Fig. 2* commonly exist in the solutions made by students. This clearly indicates the realisation of *individual learning*, since the utilisation of the smallest set of fundamental laws gives students a freedom to comply their personal strengths and preferences.

Fig. 3. Percentages of maximum exam points.

For now, our assessment of DC circuit analysis only tests the learning goals presented in chapter 2.1. Thus, learning related to questioning the validity of cornerstones is not yet really assessed. This is the aspect that we are investigating at the moment. Long-term engineering skills are not as straightforward to assess as immediate ones, but we are currently working

on this subject. However, we don't yet have reliable learning results of the long-term engineering skills to be presented here.

4 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In this paper we wanted to promote such engineering skills that cannot be easily replaced with artificial intelligence. Electrical engineering acts as a good example here, since due to its strong fundamental theory, the models of electrical engineering are rather precise in predicting electromagnetic phenomena. On the other hand, this consistency also helps to apply AI to electrical engineering tasks of industry.

Due to economical pressure and efficiency-driven development of universities during the recent decades, global worry about the state of higher learning in engineering education has risen. Typically the problem is closely related to overemphasising concrete engineering models at the expense of thorough learning of fundamentals. However, due to hierarchical structure of natural sciences, thorough learning of fundamentals is a necessity in gaining understanding about the assumptions and restrictions that validate engineering models. Such understanding represents long-term engineering skills that are not easily replaced with AI.

At Tampere University of Applied Sciences the method of cornerstones has been used in undergraduate studies of electrical engineering for about four academic year now. So far the learning results are mainly related to the principle of smallest set of fundamental rules, but the results have already been encouraging. In addition to promoting the different roles of immediate and long-term engineering skills, it seems that this kind of coherent and interconnected structure of substance also contributes to the realisation of individual learning.

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